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PEER ASSESSMENT TO IMPROVE REPRODUCIBILITY OF COMPUTATIONAL PROJECT WORK

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ABSTRACT

Computational research requires increased reproducibility for open science practices yet is not widely taught in the geosciences. Teaching reproducibility and establishing it as learning qualification and objective is an important step towards improving scientific practice and will also improve student learning by facilitating peer-review and reuse of earlier work in later courses. It will also improve the formal (summative and formative) assessment of student project work within a course, and the quality of reusable open educational resources. There is evidence in the literature that teaching reproducibility should combine practice (tutorials) trying to reproduce someone else's work, and iterations of teacher and peer feedback on the reproducibility of one's own work.

In this contribution, reproducibility was introduced as a new topic in a 15 EC MSc course, which follows a challenge-based learning approach to tackle the wicked problem of different stakeholders facing human-induced earthquakes due to gas extraction. Students work in groups for different stakeholders. Self-regulated feedback is encouraged to include other stakeholders' views. After a tutorial at the end of the first half of the course, student groups submitted a reproducibility plan for their project work, which was then peer-reviewed by the other groups, so that any feedback could still be incorporated. The quality and depth of the peer feedback itself provided information on how well the topic has been understood. The outcomes show that the approach delivered encouraging results with respect to the previous year.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation and objectives

This work is motivated by (1) the growth of study programs that address data science and computational science which require more algorithmic thinking and coding skills from students [1] and (2) the specific challenges and requirements of open and reproducible research which ask for new assessment approaches.

Reproducibility is commonly defined as the potential for a given study to be reproduced by an independent team of researchers. For example, a paper that uses a proprietary data set and only describes methods without details on parameters is not reproducible. In contrast, a study that uses open data, open-source software, and provides the full source code of the analysis workflow is highly reproducible.

Although reproducibility has always been an criterion for scientific research, several disciplines have seen a veritable reproducibility crisis: published studies and results were not reproducible with the provided information [2]. To improve the situation, we need to initiate a culture change already when teaching new scientists, and practice reproducibility as integral part of educational [3], including student assignments and project work. To be taught effectively, teaching materials need to be reproducible, reproducibility needs to be a learning objective that is assessed, and assessment itself needs to be reproducible and transparent. Since reproducibility depends on someone trying to reproduce someone else's work, it promises to be well suited to peer assessment, i.e., students attempting to reproduce other student's work and providing feedback on what worked and what did not. Peer assessment as part of peer learning has been shown to be effective for academic teaching [4], [5].

This paper describes an intervention in the context of a Senior University Teaching Qualification [6] during the MSc program Spatial Engineering (M-SE) at the University of Twente. M-SE follows principles of challenge-based learning (CBL) during three case studies of 15 EC each, which are scheduled during the first three academic quarters of the first year. They address so-called wicked problems [7], which have no clear ideal solution, but instead either several sub-optimal solutions, or even none. Since the case studies also require interdisciplinary group work, concern real-world cases, and involve multiple stakeholders, they qualify as CBL.

The intervention took place during the third case study with a cohort of 23 MSc students. For the third case study course, reproducibility is especially important for two reasons: First, M-SE assessment is focused on the process instead of outcomes, because for wicked problems no single best solution exists. To assess the process, an examiner needs to be able to reproduce it. Second, the course's main theme is legitimacy, because the case study setting is the gas extraction and resulting earthquakes in the Groningen province of the Netherlands, where years of mismanagement have dramatically reduced the trust of the various stakeholders in solutions proposed by the government or any other official authority. To re-establish trust and legitimacy, the analysis process leading to proposed policy interventions

needs transparency. Thus, the first reason is linked with the teaching and learning process and the second to course content and final qualifications.

The reproducibility of students' final reports of previous years was very low, meaning that anyone reading the reports cannot reproduce the analysis they conducted, because insufficient code or data was provided. This is not surprising for two reasons: M-SE students have diverse backgrounds and often only limited code literacy at the beginning of the course; and academic skills teaching focuses on preventing plagiarism, creating a tension with reproducible code reuse and sharing.

The goal of this work was to increase (1) the students' awareness of reproducibility, (2) their knowledge about different aspects of reproducibility (e.g., data, methods, results), and (3) skills to make their own work more reproducible. This should be reflected in increased (compared with previous years) reproducibility of the students' final reports. Further, this work provides valuable information on how and when to include reproducibility in a curriculum by answering the following questions:

1. Was the designed method, and in particular peer- and self-assessment, effective in increasing reproducibility of outcomes?
2. How do the students experience and evaluate the activities, especially the peer- and self-assessment?
3. In what way can the designed method be improved?

The first two questions will be addressed mainly in the results section, while the last question will be addressed in the discussion and reflection section.

1.2 Reproducibility in education

Although technical tools to document and assess student progress on code and project materials exist, their use within an electronic learning environment faces several challenges [8]. Early attempts included protocols for data management and analysis [9], but even more recent approaches in geoscience education [10] do not explicitly address reproducibility within the classroom, but rather that of scientific studies themselves [11], [12]. There is evidence in the literature that reproducibility is best taught by letting students take both perspectives: that of a researcher who has to design and implement his or her work reproducibly, and that of a researcher or practitioner who wants to use or validate someone else's work and reproduce it. Teaching reproducibility therefore should rely on a combination of practice (tutorials) trying to reproduce someone else's work, and iterations of teacher and peer feedback on the reproducibility of one's own work [13], [14].

A research group on reproducibility in the geosciences has developed a rubric to assess the reproducibility of research [2] as part of on-going efforts to increase reproducibility, which have led to a funded initiative to create improved author guidelines and article peer reviews for a major geoscience conference series [15]. The outcomes have provided valuable input to the presented work.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Intervention design and data

The target course runs for 10 weeks full-time (15 ECTS). It focuses on human-induced earthquakes and starts with an introductory week during which students form groups and choose a stakeholder (e.g., citizens, municipality, mining company) to represent. Week 10 is reserved for examination, leaving weeks 2-9 for student groups to design an intervention (planning, policy) that addresses the needs of their stakeholder, while acknowledging the interests of the other stakeholders. The intervention needs support from quantitative data and analysis, but also includes document studies and qualitative (interview) data and is presented by each group in a scientific report and supplementary materials, which make up 25% of the course assessment.

As mentioned, reproducibility issues can be experienced from two viewpoints: The creator of a study who needs to invest efforts to make it reproducible, and the reader who attempts the re-production. Further, literature supports the assumption that practical exercises and peer-assessment are suitable for teaching reproducibility. The intervention design takes this into account and follows four stages with new elements to the course (see Figure 1 below for the entire workflow and theory of action components):

1. Introductory information on the role of reproducibility for learning and assessment.
2. A face-to-face tutorial, consisting of four parts. First, a short lecture providing basic information, followed by two hands-on exercises to experience different viewpoints on reproducibility: assessing the reproducibility of paper, and attempting to reproduce a short mock paper with given code and data. The tutorial concluded with information about simple strategies and tools from the perspective of authors to make the scientific reports more reproducible. Further material was available on the electronic learning environment for additional self-study.
3. The self- and peer-assessment consisted of designing and assessing a reproducibility plan (RP) using a predefined template (see supplementary materials). For peer-feedback to be meaningful, students need to be able to act on it [4], which precluded peer-assessment of the final reports. Instead, all student groups had to submit the RP two days after the tutorial. In the RP, they self-assessed the current reproducibility of their project (data sources, computational workflow, outputs), then described and justified the target reproducibility, and explained the necessary measures to achieve this improvement. The RP was then peer-assessed by the other groups and reviewed by the teacher. The quality and depth of the peer feedback itself provided information on how well the topic has been understood. The feedback was formative instead of summative because the latter can lead to negative side effects and perceived disadvantages [16]–[18].
4. For the remainder of the course, the groups implemented their plans and the given feedback. They were encouraged to stay in contact with the other groups

and exchange experiences and feedback, because they all had different stakeholders to represent, yet needed to consider the viewpoints of other stakeholders as well.

The intervention used three primary data sources: First, the main data source was the scientific reports from the 2018/19 and 2019/20 academic years, with the former serving as control group. I have read and evaluated every report (in total four from 2018/19 and five from 2019/20) using the reproducibility scale developed by [2]. The reproducibility plans and the peer-feedback provided by students were the second data source, together with the final reports' reproducibility assessment addressing the first research question. The third data source was the course evaluation during and after the course, which included specific questions on reproducibility and thus provides valuable feedback to address research questions 2 and 3.

Figure 1: Conceptual workflow developing and designing the intervention; the dotted arrow indicates a feedback loop for the current (2020/21) course

2.2 Implementation

The first introduction to the intervention was part of the general course introduction (including assignments) on the first day of the course. A reminder and more detail was given during a tutoring session in the second week.

The main face-to-face activity was a tutorial at the beginning of week 6. While this was relatively late in the process, the students have to face many organizational challenges in the start-up phase, and if taught too early, a 'minor' issue like reproducibility might "go under".

The execution of the tutorial was heavily impacted by the Covid-19-related short-notice closure of the university buildings, and the decision of the university management to halt all teaching activities during that week. Since no information was provided what this imposed educational lockdown meant for the remainder of

the academic calendar nor for the assessments, this was a very difficult situation. The tutorial was declared as “experimental teaching”, preparing students for future online education, and several adjustments had to be made for online teaching. Overall attendance was very high (18 out of 23 enrolled students), with participants from every group present.

Four of the five groups submitted the RP and its peer-assessment and received further feedback from the teacher. Once the groups reports were submitted, I graded those, with feedback on reproducibility being part of the overall feedback.

The first evaluation of the implementation process took place right after the tutorial (please see supplementary materials), which 10 out of the 18 students completed. After the completion of the entire course, students could provide individual detailed feedback during a second evaluation, during which 13 students answered (see Results section).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Reproducibility of the scientific reports

To address the first question on the measurable effect within the course, the reproducibility of the final deliverables (one scientific report per student group) from 2020 was compared to that of the previous year 2019.

To briefly summarize the approach to scoring reproducibility (for details see [2]): Reproducibility of research can be measured along three main dimensions: Input data, processing/analysis, and output. Each of these three dimensions can achieve one of four levels:

Unavailable (a score of 0 in the following tables) indicates that there was no information on where to retrieve the input, how the computations ran, and how the outputs were created. Normally, no peer-reviewed publication should receive such a score in any dimension.

Documented (a score of 1) indicates that there is no direct access to datasets, that executable code is unavailable or proprietary software was used, and results may be incomplete. In contrast to *Unavailable*, the descriptions and metadata are likely sufficient to recreate the study given enough time and resources.

Available (a score of 2) was assigned if direct access to the materials (data, code, full results) is provided (e.g., through a link to a personal or institutional website or in supplementary materials), but not in the form of an open and permanent identifier, such as a digital object identifier (DOI). The students were encouraged to submit all materials in a supplementary archive, with an online repository being an option.

The gold standard of *Open* access (score of 3) requires open and permanent access to all materials (e.g., through public online repositories with a DOI) and open licenses to allow use and extension. This level was not expected from student submissions.

The following Table 1 provides the reproducibility scores for data/processing/results and short teacher feedback to justify those scores.

Table 1. Reproducibility of scientific reports in 2019 (pre-intervention) and 2020 (post-intervention)

Student group	2019		2020	
	scores	teacher assessment	scores	teacher assessment
1	1/1/1	links to important input data provided (not clear if to all required), but otherwise not enough information to understand details of the analysis	0/0/1	No reproducibility plan handed in; report is practically irreproducible, too much information is missing
2	0/1/1	very little concrete information on data or computational environment	1/2/2	reproducibility plan is short and vague, but addresses all main items, showing some thought; final report has very little information on the input data, but extensive information on the analysis in several appendices
3	1/0/0	many links to data sources (again unclear if all), but very little information on processing and results	1/1/1	reproducibility plan is quite good, and even has more information than the final report, very little information on any aspect of the analysis
4	1/1/1	Overall reproducibility low, but group analysed in detail the reproducibility of other sources, so there is at least an understanding of the problem	2/1/2	good reproducibility plan with clear, achievable targets; final report tried to provide as much material as possible, also in appendices, data is available through links
5	NA	NA	1/1/1	detailed reproducibility plan, although the group scored existing situation too high; final report shows little concern for reproducibility

In summary, in 2019 no group scored higher than 1 (or *Documented*) on reproducibility dimensions. In (post-intervention) 2020, four of the five groups handed in a reproducibility report as requested, and although none of the scientific reports are fully reproducible (i.e., reaching a score of 2, or *Available*), there is a clear improvement over 2019. The only group that did not hand in a reproducibility report

also scored the lowest on reproducibility. Of the other four groups, two groups achieved scores of 2 in some dimensions, but two groups also fell short of their ambitions and only achieved the minimum scores of 1.

One potential reason for low scores in 2020 is that groups did less quantitative or computational analysis than planned, and conceptual and qualitative work is more difficult to reproduce. The reasons for the deviation from the plans are not mentioned explicitly in the course evaluation, but there is evidence from the course evaluation that it is linked to the impact of Covid-19 (e.g., difficulties to share work and results).

3.2 Evaluation of intervention by students

To address the second research question on how the students evaluate the intervention and the different activities, the tutorial feedback right after the session provides valuable information and was mostly positive:

Table 2. Tutorial evaluation right after the course (number of responses, different totals per question are the result of not all students responding)

How useful did you find the ...	Not useful	A bit useful	Quite useful	Very useful
introductory lecture on reproducibility?	0	2	5	3
first part of the exercise (reading the paper and scoring it)?	0	0	7	3
second part of the exercise (running example code)?	1	4	4	1
information on reproducibility strategies and recommendations?	0	1	4	5

Students also provided comments. The majority of those addressed the issue that they had very different backgrounds, and while some expressed the wish for more practical examples to try out, others struggled with the given examples in the time they had. More collaboration and possibly working in pairs is another suggestion. The following two example commentaries summarize most of the feedback:

“Unfortunately, it's not easy to choose the proper exercises since we all come from different backgrounds and have different experiences related to the topic. Perhaps by guaranteeing time to work both individually and in small groups might help (where people can help each other and share knowledge). I understand that this might be much easier when sitting in the same room rather than with online sessions (but I guess it's just a matter of getting familiar with other platforms to share screens for example, etc.)”

"Giving a little more time to do exercise as many students have different speed and knowledge on how they work. (Applies both) Otherwise, it was a good learning experience. I learnt an entire new thing and its importance. "

While the immediate evaluation after the tutorial points out the utility of the exercises, the later overall course evaluation rates the utility for the course a bit lower, while the utility for the entire curriculum is seen more positive. This reflects that the fact that many students did not seem to be able to reach the point in their project analysis where reproducibility would have become more important.

Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding the tutorial on reproducibility.

Fig. 2. Tutorial evaluation during the standard course evaluation

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The formative assessment of the reproducibility activities facilitated peer-feedback because it removed hesitations on the part of the students to criticize their peers and cause low marks for them. Most of the students had little to no experience with systematic peer-feedback and -assessment. Overall, working with student groups is easier than working with individual students (at least for larger classes). The tutorial also showed to be adaptable to full online teaching because it relied on working individually with someone else's materials. Considering the short time frame that was available to change major parts of the intervention to full online (two working days for the tutorial), this transition went very well.

Regarding the question whether the designed method was effective in introducing reproducibility and significantly increase the students' reproducibility scores, the course evaluation and related discussion show that the impact of the Covid-19 makes it impossible to draw robust conclusions here. It affected the way of working

massively in the middle of the course. Some student groups were able to deal with this more effectively than others. Most groups have better reproducible scientific reports than in the previous year, but not all, and the overall level is still not *Available*. The low level of computational spatial analysis in many of the scientific reports, for which the new materials would have been most applicable, might be a factor. Nevertheless, the results show that students found this new topic interesting. Even students with limited computational background reported raised awareness about the issue, and for them the intervention provided a lot of pointers to further information, new tools, and other learning opportunities. How many of these will be used in the long-term was outside the scope of this intervention, but I will examine the impact on the reproducibility of the students' MSc thesis reports in summer 2021.

Regarding the question how the students experienced and evaluated the activities, the clear majority found the course-based activities (i.e., the tutorial and the writing and peer-reviewing of the reproducibility plan) useful and considered it relevant for both the course and their further studies, and readily participated in the voluntary activities. This suggests sufficient reason to keep them in the course.

The last question addressed the issue in what way the designed method could be improved. Given that the topic is quite new to many students, feedback indicates that some more time for the teaching and self-assessment would be valuable. This would also mean to anchor the topic in the learning objectives and make sure to test it.

This academic year saw the repetition of the tutorial and reproducibility plan, making only very minor changes (e.g., correcting mistakes, adjusting the schedule to the different academic year) and improvements to content. The outcomes of this year will be presented at the conference and provide more evidence for robust statements about effectiveness and efficacy of the approach. Based on these insights, for the next academic year of 2021/22, plans are to expand the tutorial to two half-days, and introduce reproducibility clearly as a tested learning objective, and therefore make participation in the reproducibility plan and its peer-review mandatory. Further, I plan to coordinate and link the activities with further project proposals and activities on reproducibility in the University of Twente's open science community.

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